

THE EXPERIENCE OF DEVELOPING PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN GERMANY

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Abstract. *Public administration is a system that is crucial for the political, social and economic stability of each country. Countries form models of governance based on their historical, cultural and legal characteristics. The Federal Republic of Germany is one of the countries that is notable for creating an effective, transparent and citizen-friendly model of public administration. This article analyzes the main approaches to the development of public administration in Germany, its institutional reforms and the significance of this experience for other countries.*

Keywords: *federalism, digital public administration, innovative approaches, reduction of bureaucracy.*

Formation of the public administration system in Germany

Formation of the modern public administration system in Germany is inextricably linked with the Basic Law (Grundgesetz), adopted in 1949. This constitution established Germany as a federal state and divided the powers of governance between the federal government and the state governments (Landes).

The principle of federalism created a decentralized, but at the same time coordinated form of public administration. In this model, the federal government is responsible for general government issues such as foreign policy, defense and monetary policy, while the states pursue independent policies in the areas of education, culture, police and homeland administration.

Public Administration Reforms and Their Content

A number of reforms have been implemented in Germany in recent decades to effectively organize public administration. These include the following:

a) Implementation of the principles of New Public Management

Since the 1990s, Germany has been trying to integrate market mechanisms into public administration. In this direction, public authorities have also begun to implement methods used in the private sector, such as efficiency, effectiveness and customer focus. The performance of civil servants is assessed on the basis of KPIs (key performance indicators).

b) Development of e-Government

Since the 2000s, the transition to digital public administration has accelerated in Germany. E-services have made it easier for citizens and businesses to communicate with government agencies. The BundOnline 2005 program was an important step towards moving public services online. Today, many services are automated via the Deutschland-Online platform.

c) Reducing bureaucracy

In Germany, the Bürokratieabbau program was introduced to reduce bureaucratic barriers. This program aims to reduce unnecessary paperwork and simplify processes for businesses and citizens.

d) Increasing accountability and responsibility

In order to increase the transparency of public organizations, annual reporting, auditing, and public oversight systems were strengthened. This helped to increase citizen participation in public affairs.

Results of the digitalization process in public administration in Germany

In Germany, more than 600 services were digitized via the Deutschland-Online platform in 2021. As a result, the number of online users of public services increased from 23% in 2010 to 78% in 2020 (according to OECD data). These figures show how important digital transformation is for user experience.

Table 1

Comparative analysis of public administration reforms

Name of the reform	Year of issue	Purpose	Efficiency
New Public Management	1990- years	Increase efficiency	KPI system, result orientation
BundOnline 2005	2000–2005 years	Implementation of electronic services	400+ services digitized
Bürokratieabbau	2006–2010 years	Decrease bureaucracy	The number of redundant documents has been reduced
Deutschland-Online	from 2010 year	Complex digital transformation	The share of online services is 78%

Main advantages of the German governance model

Public administration in Germany has a number of important advantages:

For balancing based on the principle of federalism - powers are clearly divided between central and local authorities. Such a system increases responsibility and allows decisions to be made in accordance with local needs.

Innovative approaches - the widespread introduction of digital technologies improves the quality of governance.

Increasing citizen trust - ensuring openness of government activities, forming trusting relationships with citizens.

Strong legal foundations - the independence of the Basic Law and the judicial system are factors that limit and control government bodies.

The importance of German experience for Uzbekistan

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been working in such important areas as reforming public administration, open dialogue with citizens, and introducing electronic services. The German experience can serve as an example for Uzbekistan in the following aspects:

Implementation of individual elements of federalism - increasing the independence of local authorities and strengthening their accountability.

Deepening e-government - ensuring transparency and efficiency through the digitalization of public services.

Active participation of citizens – strengthening mechanisms for taking public opinion into account in public administration.

Reduction of bureaucracy – simplification of public services by eliminating unnecessary formalities.

Table 2

Level of development of e-government in Germany and Uzbekistan

Index	Germany (2023)	Uzbekistan (2023)
Electronic Government Development Index (EGDI)	0.9153 (very high)	0.6374 (average)
Share of digital services	78%	32%
Number of state web portals	150+	40+
Digitization at local level	To an acceptable degree	At the initial stage

(Source: UN E-Government Survey 2022)

Recommendations based on the German experience:

- Clearly define the powers of local authorities in Uzbekistan and encourage them to make independent decisions;
- Provide electronic public services in a “one-stop-shop” manner;
- Introduce a system for evaluating the activities of public employees based on KPI;
- Strengthen mechanisms that legally guarantee public participation.

Conclusion

The experience of the development of German public administration serves as an important example in creating a system that prioritizes efficiency, transparency, and the interests of citizens. This experience is an area that should be studied by other countries, including Uzbekistan.

If legal, technological, and institutional approaches, such as those in Germany, are successfully applied during the reforms, public administration will reach a qualitatively new level.

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